

УДК 330.3

*Kostiantyn Berest*ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AS A TOOL FOR INCREASING
THE COMPETITIVENESS OF A MODERN IT COMPANY

This article focuses on the importance and relevance of the artificial intelligence (AI) usage by modern IT companies and enterprises operating in the digital field. The article examines the most common proven ways of using AI by the service providers and product creators (both physical and digital). There are also the methods and areas of AI application by Ukrainian IT companies given. In addition, the author emphasizes the ambiguity of the influence caused by the involvement of AI by modern companies both on the competitiveness of the economic entities themselves and on the market as a whole - in particular, on the fairness of competition and the possibility of the new players appearance on the market. The article states that currently the use of AI in production or service provision is not a factor in increasing the company's competitiveness, because there are high risks associated with its uncontrolled use.

Key words: artificial intelligence, AI, IT companies, development, production, competitiveness.

Берест К. В. Штучний інтелект як інструмент підвищення конкурентоспроможності сучасної ІТ компанії.

Ця стаття фокусується на важливості та актуальності використання штучного інтелекту (ШІ) сучасними ІТ компаніями та підприємствами, що функціонують у цифровому полі. У статті розглянуто найбільш поширені підтвержені способи використання ШІ у наданні послуг та створенні нових продуктів (як фізичних так і цифрових). Також наведено способи та галузі застосування ШІ українськими ІТ компаніями. Окрім цього, автором зроблено акцент на неоднозначності впливу залучення ШІ сучасними компаніями як на конкурентоспроможність самих суб'єктів господарювання, так і на ринок в цілому – зокрема на чесність конкуренції та можливість появи нових гравців на ринку. У статті зазначено, що наразі саме використання ШІ у виробництві чи наданні послуг не є фактором підвищення конкурентоспроможності компанії, адже існують високі ризики, пов'язані з його безконтрольним використанням.

Ключові слова: штучний інтелект, ІТ-компанії, розробка, виробництво, конкурентоспроможність.

Problem statement: usage of the artificial intelligence (AI) remains relevant for modern IT companies and any companies operating in the digital world. Most analysts consider AI usage to be beneficial in development and production. However, an increasing number of researchers and practitioners emphasize the ambiguity of using AI as a method to enhance a company's competitiveness due to inadequate regulation and risks associated with data loss and even reputation damage.

Literature and recent research review: modern analysts [1, 2, 6, 8] emphasize that the main benefit of using AI by modern IT companies is to speed up their routine tasks completion and data processing, reduce inefficient work done by people and even increase the level of product personalization at lower cost. However, in recent research one paid attention to the ethics [4, 5] and security [3] of the AI usage. At the same time, the search for a unique formula for the safe and effective AI usage remains an open question.

The purpose of the article is to identify the most common practices of successful and safe use of AI by modern IT companies in order to increase their competitiveness.

There are several most common ways of using artificial intelligence to increase the competitiveness of IT companies:

- Improvement of products and services: AI allows companies to create more innovative products and services that can be more quickly and easily adjusted to the personal needs of each individual user [8]. This allows one to increase sales and retain old customers without significant changes in the core product.
- Optimization of processes: AI is actively used not only to automate internal business processes and logistics, but also to improve customer service [1]. This allows companies to reduce costs, increase productivity and thus increase competitiveness.
- Improved analytics and decision support: AI analyzes large volumes of data and can provide analytical support for strategic planning and decision-making, helping companies identify the best opportunities and growth strategies [7].
- Improved security: AI can be used to detect and prevent cyberattacks and other security threats, which is especially important for IT companies

whose main asset is information. Thus, AI helps modern companies partially reduce their operational risks.

However, the last point becomes more and more questionable lately, because AI is both a way to reduce the risks of external interference and a way to lose critical information due to employees' voluntary non-compliance with information security guidelines. For the same reason, we do not see much interest in the use of AI by public or government institutions.

At the same time, the vast majority of analytical reviews of recent years [2, 3] agree that the active use of AI by modern IT companies is no longer a future trend, because the core of many world-famous products already contains solutions built on the use of AI:

- Thus, Google uses AI to improve its products and services, such as the search engine, translator, YouTube and Google Photos [9]. AI improves the search results, filters harmful content, and identifies potentially offensive content.
- Amazon uses AI to automate its logistics operations, inventory management, and demand forecasting [10]. This allows them to quickly process orders and ensure fast delivery to customers.
- Facebook uses AI to analyze and categorize content, recognize faces and filter inappropriate content. This helps to increase the users security and makes the product more convenient [6].
- Tesla is implementing AI-based autopilot systems for autonomous cars development [2].
- Netflix uses AI for recommendations personalization - the search and suggestions engines adjust results according to one's watchlist preferences and choices [5]. This helps increase the number of subscribers and reduce the churn rate.

It is obvious that the global technological giants benefit from AI usage. The vast majority of these companies use their own AI solutions, so, in fact, the use of AI for them is not something fundamentally new - it is only the implementation of long-term development plans. It is important to understand that often the investments and actual costs for such changes in production or service provision were made by these companies in the past decades, so currently most of them have moved from finding the validity

of such investments to optimizing return on investment, maximizing profits and maintaining their market dominance [8].

It is also worth noting that the use of artificial intelligence raises the question of fair competition existence, because AI can help monopolists maintain their dominant position in the market, since this technology provides them with a number of competitive advantages and can be used to strengthen their leadership [4, 5]. Regulation and supervision of the use of AI in monopolistic structures are urgent and difficult tasks for authorities and society.

However, AI continues to be purely a tool, and therefore, like no other tool or production technology, it cannot be evaluated as an exclusively positive or negative economic phenomenon. Fortunately, the effectiveness of many AI models directly depends on the number of its users and the amount of data available to that network. This, in turn, leads to the fact that AI products are often open for use, so small and medium-sized businesses and even individual entrepreneurs are actively involved in the development of new technology in their production.

For instance, Ukrainian trends in AI usage by domestic IT companies (mainly companies represented on the Ukrainian market) are almost no different from global trends [8]. There are several main ways of using AI:

- Text analysis and speech recognition: many Ukrainian IT companies use AI to analyze text information. For example, some companies develop programs for analyzing social networks and news portals in order to identify trends and public sentiments.
- Customer support: the vast majority of Ukrainian IT companies use AI-based chat-bots to communicate with their customers and solve their queries in real time.
- Medical diagnostics: some Ukrainian IT companies unite with medical institutions to develop AI systems for diagnostics. These systems can help doctors in early disease detection and medical images analysis.
- Financial services: more and more financial companies are using AI-based information services for risk analysis, forecasting market trends and automating asset management processes.
- Gaming industry: Ukrainian video game developers actively use AI to create intelligent and realistic gameplay, create new scenes and other content.

- Agriculture: Ukrainian agro-technological companies use AI to monitor crop conditions, forecast yields and optimize agricultural processes.

In conclusion, we can state that the impact of artificial intelligence usage by modern companies is similar in its effect to the revolutionary impact of Internet access in the last century. Although artificial intelligence is not a stand-alone or core means of ensuring the company's competitiveness, it significantly simplifies production processes and improves the provision of services. As a result - one can allocate free resources for more creative and complex tasks, which leads to more effective resources spent and increases ROI.

There is still an open question of the unevenness of regulatory restrictions on the use of AI in certain industries and state-owned companies. This question is to be covered in future research.

References

1. Agrawal, A., McHale, J., & Oettl, A. (2018). Finding needles in haystacks: Artificial intelligence and recombinant growth. In *The economics of artificial intelligence: An agenda* (pp. 149-174). Chicago: University of Chicago Press. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w24541>
2. Ajitha, P. V., & Nagra, A. (2021). An Overview of Artificial Intelligence in Automobile Industry—A Case Study on Tesla Cars. *Solid State Technology*, 64(2), 503-512. <https://doi.org/10.47992/ijaeml.2581.7000.0113>
3. Davenport, T. H., & Ronanki, R. (2018). Artificial intelligence for the real world. *Harvard business review*, 96(1), 108-116. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojbm.2022.101026>
4. Coeckelbergh, M. (2019). Artificial intelligence: some ethical issues and regulatory challenges. *Technology and regulation*, 2019 (2019), 31-34. <https://doi.org/10.26116/techreg.2019.003>
5. Gupta, D. G., & Jain, V. (2023). Use of Artificial Intelligence with Ethics and Privacy for Personalized Customer Services. In *Artificial Intelligence in Customer Service: The Next Frontier for Personalized Engagement* (pp. 231-257). Cham: Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-33898-4_10
6. Kachamas, P., Akkaradamrongrat, S., Sinthupinyo, S., & Chandrachai, A. (2019). Application of artificial intelligence in the prediction of consumer behavior from Facebook posts analysis. *International Journal of Machine Learning and Computing*, 9(1), 91-97. <https://doi.org/10.18178/ijmlc.2019.9.1.770>

7. Liebrechts, W., Darnihamedani, P., Postma, E., & Atzmueller, M. (2020). The promise of social signal processing for research on decision-making in entrepreneurial contexts. *Small business economics*, 55(3), 589-605. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-019-00205-1>

8. Obschonka, M., & Audretsch, D. B. (2020). Artificial intelligence and big data in entrepreneurship: a new era has begun. *Small Business Economics*, 55(3), 529-539. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-019-00202-4>

9. Yanisky-Ravid, S., & Martens, C. (2019). From the Myth of Babel to Google Translate: Confronting Malicious Use of Artificial Intelligence-Copyright and Algorithmic Biases in Online Translations Systems. *Seattle University Law Review*, 43(1), 1-80. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3345716>

10. Zwakman, D. S., Pal, D., & Arpnikanondt, C. (2021). Usability evaluation of artificial intelligence-based voice assistants: The case of Amazon Alexa. *SN Computer Science*, 2, 28. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42979-020-00424-4>